

EXPLORING (EMERGING) MYCOTOXINS RISK IN BEANS: A GLOBAL ALLIANCE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE RESILIENCE

D1.1 – Report on the identification of toxigenic fungi species from beans

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RESPONSIBLE AUTHORS	Chiara Dall'Asta (UNIPR) Awanwee Petchkongkaew (TU)

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1.0	Initial Version	23/02/2025	Chiara Dall'Asta (UNIPR) Awanwee Petchkongkaew (TU)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The overall scope of the Deliverable 1.1 – Report on the identification of toxigenic fungi species from beans is to provide information about the activities carried out for fungal identification in beans and pulses. The first goal is to define a list of relevant fungi which may potentially grow on beans and legumes. This is very relevant for the identification of proper mycotoxin targets for further activities under the Mycobeaons project. Such list of fungi has been agreed among the partnership based on scientific literature and occurrence data. In addition, the project aims at developing a rapid diagnostic protocol for fungal identification. During the first year, the partners have exchanged their knowledge and started aligning the protocols for the development of a proper DNA-based tool.

Mycobeaons is an initiative under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Staff Exchange, which is part of the Horizon Europe Programme. It involves a consortium of participants that includes both Beneficiaries and Associated Partners from institutions of higher education, public research organizations, and private sector companies, having already adopted measures to ensure open science practices, particularly in the management of research data. These facts will help towards a smooth adoption of the relative open science principles required under MSCA actions implementation.

1. Current scenario from the scientific literature

MycobEons is committed to increase the knowledge about fungal incidence and mycotoxins occurrence in alternative protein sources of plant origin, mainly pulses and beans.

To gain a clearer understanding of which fungal strains might impact beans and pulses, an examination of the scientific literature and available resources has been conducted.

Legumes belong to the *Leguminosae* family and encompass seeds such as soybeans, as well as pulses like peas, chickpeas, lentils, lupines, and beans¹. Among the proteins derived from legumes, soybeans (*Glycine max*) are the most extensively utilized, attributed to their availability, superior nutritional quality, functional properties, and high protein content^{1,2}. However, given the increasing controversy surrounding soy as a commodity due to concerns regarding its environmental and social sustainability³, there is a rising interest in employing proteins from other beans for plant-based substitutes of animal products.

Like other crops, legumes are vulnerable to fungal infections, which pose potential health risks due to the ability of some fungi to produce mycotoxins. Mycotoxins are toxic secondary metabolites generated by certain filamentous fungi, either before or after harvest, under favourable environmental conditions. Although it is known that fungi may infect beans and pulses, especially those belonging to *Aspergillus* spp. and *Penicillium* spp., there are still gaps in the current literature when it comes to chickpea, pea, lentils and beans. On the contrary, the body of knowledge existing for soy and peanuts is more extensive.

Due to the combination of climate change, the prevalence of toxicogenic fungi has significantly been increasing worldwide, with a shift from the tropical area towards poles. This is of particular concern in developing countries due to factors such as unfavourable climate, inadequate production technologies and insufficient crop storage facilities.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814874-7.00006-7>

² <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10020293>

³ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-015-0931-6>

2. Toxigenic fungi potentially infecting beans and pulses

Although the first reports on the capacity of fungi to grow on pulses started down in the '70s^{4,5}, the occurrence of mycotoxins in these commodities has been addressed less frequently than other crops, such as cereals and products thereof⁶.

While pulses and beans have been associated with all the main mycotoxins (i.e. aflatoxins, ochratoxin A, trichothecenes and fumonisins), fungi belonging to *Aspergillus* spp, *Penicillium* spp., *Alternaria* spp. and *Fusarium* spp. are those more often reported in legumes.

It is known that fungal colonization is highly related to environmental conditions both at pre- and post harvest⁷. Climate, agronomic parameters and post-harvest conditions may indeed favour and modulate fungal infection in a crop-specific way, as demonstrated for many crops, including cereals, vegetables, and fruits^{8,9}, but less information is available for pulses also in terms of crop management and mycotoxin mitigation along the production chain.

Although cereals are considered most susceptible to fungal growth than pulses and beans, the filamentous fungi may affect legumes at several stages of the supply chain. Warm and humid climates are particularly conducive to the growth of toxinogenic fungi, making regions with such climates more susceptible to contamination¹⁰. Poor storage conditions, such as high humidity and temperature, can also exacerbate the problem by promoting fungal growth and toxin production.

Very recently, Sbai et al. (2024)¹¹ reviewed the most common fungal pathogens affecting legume crops, providing a list of the major pathogens isolated from pulses. In particular, *Fusarium oxysporium* and *F. solani* are two common pathogens responsible for Fusarium wilt disease and have been isolated worldwide. The same authors listed several fungal metabolites, among them the non regulated mycotoxins beauvericin (BEA), enniatins (ENNs), and fusarins (FUSs). In addition, *F. moniliforme* and *P. citrinum* have been reported in beans, too¹²

⁴ [https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0142\(197107\)28:1<253::aid-cnrc2820280151>3.0.co;2-g](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0142(197107)28:1<253::aid-cnrc2820280151>3.0.co;2-g)

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028X-41.5.375>

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.13008>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2017.01.011>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2007.07.060>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules21050627>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2017.11.009>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2024.101447>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1162595>

3. Fungal Identification Strategy covered by Mycobeaons project

It should be noted that the primary focus of Mycobeaons project is the occurrence of mycotoxins, with the ultimate goal to provide a toolbox for mitigation and management in alternative proteins from beans and pulses. Therefore, fungal isolation is not among the activities covered by the project. However, in the light of the climate change, collecting information about fungal incidence and growth will help in designing proper managing measures for mycotoxin mitigation both in the field and at post-harvest.

Therefore, the Mycobeaons Consortium has planned to develop a highly efficient algorithm to analyze fungal genome data and obtain and validate species-specific DNA markers. Such markers and DNA-based detection assays can accelerate detection and surveillance of fungal contamination in food and feed.

Since both short-reads and long-reads methodologies were available among partners, a study visit of researchers from Mahidol University (Thailand) has been organised to University of Parma in October 2024 to discuss and compare available techniques. During the study visit, 6 researchers from MU and a group of chemists and microbiologist from UNIPR have exchanged knowledge and practical expertise about the use of the orthogonal Illumina™ (available at UNIPR) and Nanopore™ (available at MU) technologies. To maximise the impact, the MU delegation has organised a workshop involving students and young researchers from UNIPR (a total of 30 undergrad students and 20 among PhD and PostDoc researchers) to illustrate the potential of Nanopore technology. The flyer of the workshop is provided as Annex 1 to this deliverable.

Following the workshop, one researcher from Mahidol remained at UNIPR for a 2 months secondment, to further deepen protocols and methodologies. Given the very promising results, UNIPR has purchased a portable Nanopore MinIon device for rapid DNA sequencing. The technique was then thoroughly tested under the supervision of the secondee, and DNA extraction protocols were discussed and aligned. During the secondment, the bioinformatics pipelines for data analysis have been also exchanged and discussed.

After the end of the secondment, both groups are in contact to continue the protocol development and first preliminary data analysis. Over the next year, a secondment is planned from UNIPR to MU for the analysis of fungal genome according to the aligned protocols.

The overall goal is to provide a protocol for rapid DNA sequencing and on-site fungal identification to support mycotoxins management in the field. In addition, Nanopore and Illumina methodologies will be compared and integrated to maximise the understanding. This will help in developing appropriate management and mitigation guidelines and information packages for farmers and producers. Available data will be delivered with a practical demonstration to the relevant stakeholders, among them the policy makers, in order to support risk assessment and proper management initiatives.

NANOPORE™ TECHNOLOGY - Nanopore technology is a cutting-edge method for DNA sequencing that allows for the real-time analysis of DNA or RNA molecules as they pass through tiny pores, or nanopores, in a membrane. Nanopores are small holes embedded in an electro-resistant membrane. Each nanopore is connected to an electrode and a sensor chip that measures the electric current flowing through the nanopore. When a DNA or RNA molecule passes through a nanopore, it disrupts the current, creating a unique signal or “squiggle” that corresponds to the sequence of nucleotide bases (A, T, G, C for DNA; A, U, G, C for RNA). Among the key features of the technique, Nanopore sequencing provides real time analysis and scalability, with the possibility to use portable devices as well as high-throughput systems. In addition, it can sequence native DNA or RNA without the need for amplification or labelling, allowing for the detection of base modifications and ultra-long reads. Therefore, the method is particularly suitable for rapid on-site analysis, also in terms of early detection.

ILLUMINA™ TECHNOLOGY - The Illumina technique is a widely used method for DNA sequencing, known for its high accuracy and scalability. As a first step, DNA is fragmented into smaller pieces, and adapters are added to the ends of these fragments. The fragments are then attached to a flow cell and amplified to form clusters through a process called bridge amplification. This creates millions of copies of each fragment in a small area. During sequencing, fluorescently labeled nucleotides are added one at a time. Each nucleotide emits a unique fluorescent signal when incorporated into the DNA strand. These signals are captured by a detector and the sequence of DNA is determined based on the order of the fluorescent signals.

Illumina™ methodology can process millions of DNA fragments simultaneously, making it suitable for whole-genome sequencing. It is highly accurate, but time- and cost-demanding. Therefore, while it can be regarded as the technique of choice for large research projects, it is not suited for rapid diagnostics. On the other side, Nanopore™ is less comprehensive, but thanks to the scalability and portability it can be successfully used for on-field analysis.

ANNEX 1

Nanopore Sequencing Technology and Bioinformatics October 2024, University of Parma, Italy

Day/Time	Activity	Speaker
Day 1		
8:45-9:00	Check-in	Participants
9:00-9:15	Opening	Prof. Dr. Chiara Dall'Asta
9:15-10:40	Introduction to Oxford Nanopore Technologies & Applications	Tip
10:40-10:50	Q&A / break	
10:50-11:10	Bioinformatics for nanopore data	Piroon
11:10-12:00	Hands-on Session: Flow Cell Loading	Si-LoL team
12:00-13:00	Lunch	
13:00-15:00	Discussion and Exploration of Common Interests	Parma team & Si-LoL team
15:00-15:15	Wrap up	Prof. Dr. Chiara Dall'Asta
Day 2		
9:00-10:30	Memorandum of Understanding between the Faculty of Medicine Siriraj Hospital, Mahidol University and the University of Parma	Prof. Paolo Martelli, Prof. Dr. Chiara Dall'Asta, & Si-LoL team

Si-LoL: Siriraj Long-read Lab
Visit our website: <https://www.longreadlab.com/>

What is Nanopore Sequencing?

Nanopore sequencing is a revolutionary technology that provides real-time data and long-read sequencing capabilities, allowing for comprehensive coverage of complex genomes. It uses a protein nanopore set in an electrically resistant polymer membrane. As DNA strands pass through the nanopore, changes in the electrical conductivity are detected and used to identify the sequence of bases in real-time. This technology is particularly effective for applications like whole-genome sequencing, targeted resequencing, and monitoring microbial processes in fermentation.